

BMF CP85: Childhood residential proximity to the coast, nature connectedness, and peace of mind

AISDL Team

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“When you meditate to the point where the Eight Winds no longer disturb your mind, confusion will vanish, and your wisdom will shine like the full moon.

—In “The Philosophy of Awakening”; [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

[COLLABORATIVE PROJECT]

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is the residential proximity to the coast during childhood, and nature connectedness, associated with peace of mind when visiting the coast?
- Does the residential proximity to the coast during childhood moderate the relationship between nature connectedness and peace of mind when visiting the coast?
- How is the peace of mind associated with improved thinking when visiting the coast?

1.2. Materials

The granular interaction thinking of mindsponge theory will be used for the conceptual development of this study, while Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be used for statistical analysis [1-4]. The dataset comprises 1939 responses from the adult Flemish population about their visits to the Belgian coast [5]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [6]. For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/13844677>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis shows that nature connectedness and the residential proximity to the coast during childhood are positively associated with peace of mind when visiting the coast, but the relationship between nature connectedness and peace of mind when visiting the coast is negatively moderated by the residential proximity to the coast during childhood (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Estimated coefficients

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps for registering to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**

AISDL members who have joined this project: Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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[4] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4922461>

[5] Hooyberg A, et al. (2024). Survey data linking coastal visit behaviours to socio-demographic and health profiles. *Scientific Data*, **11**, 315. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-024-03161-y>

[6] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). bayesvl: Visually Learning the Graphical Structure of Bayesian Networks and Performing MCMC with 'Stan'. *The Comprehensive R Archive Network*. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/bayesvl/index.html>

[7] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

